

ELEVATED TEMPERATURE PROPERTIES OF SiC WHISKER REINFORCED ALUMINUM

William L. Phillips

U.S. Naval Research Laboratory
Washington, D.C. 20375

Introduction

Metal matrix composites made with strong, stiff whiskers have not been used in structural applications because their properties are not good enough to justify the extremely high costs of the whiskers that run into the hundreds, or even thousands, of dollars per kilogram (1,2). Recently, a new manufacturing process has been developed for making very small, inexpensive SiC whiskers from rice hulls which are a low-cost by-product of the food processing industry. The cost of aluminum matrix composites made with these whiskers will depend on many factors, including the production volume. An estimate of \$22/kg (\$10/lb) appears to be realistic for structural shapes with 30 volume percent reinforcement provided the composites can be mass produced using inexpensive casting and extrusion methods. If the cost can be held to this level, even a modest increase in mechanical properties, over the properties obtainable with unreinforced metals, will make these composites economically competitive for a wide range of high performance structural applications.

The objectives of this research were twofold. First, to determine if the SiC whiskers produced from rice hulls could be successfully manufactured into aluminum matrix composites by pressure casting ingots with a random fiber orientation and then warm extruding the ingots to produce a good degree of fiber alignment, and second, to evaluate the short time elevated temperature strength and stiffness of the SiC/2024 Al composite so manufactured.

Materials and Testing Procedure

The single crystal SiC whiskers were manufactured by Silag, Inc., a joint venture of Exxon Corp. and Commercial Technology, Inc. One of the reasons for the potentially low cost of these whiskers is that they are made from rice hulls, which are available from food processors at a minimal charge. It was estimated by the whisker manufacturer that 65% of the SiC is in the form of whiskers. These whiskers are mostly hexagonal in cross-section, but, for simplicity, are approximated by equivalent diameters of 0.2 to 0.5 μm (8 to 20 μ inches) and have length to diameter ratios of roughly 80. The remainder of the material is in the form of small SiC particles.

SiC whiskers, along with the small SiC particles, were fabricated into composites by Divecha Associates using a proprietary process that consisted of liquid metal infiltrating the fiber reinforcement with 2024 Al at $670 \pm 20^\circ\text{C}$ ($1240 \pm 36^\circ\text{F}$) (3). The resulting 25 mm (1.00 inch) diameter by 32 mm (1.25 inch) long ingots had a random fiber orientation before they were extruded into 6.4 mm (0.25 inch) diameter rods at a temperature of $480 \pm 50^\circ\text{C}$ ($900 \pm 90^\circ\text{F}$). The 16:1 area reduction during extrusion was designed to put the material in a more useable dimensional form and to give the fibers a good degree of alignment in the axial direction. A 9.5 mm (0.375 inch) thick disc was placed in front of each billet before extrusion to clad the composite and to prevent the die from being abraded by the fibers. For comparison purposes, unreinforced 2024 Al control billets were cast and extruded by the same process and at the same temperature. This aluminum alloy was chosen as the matrix material because of its high strength when heat treated. In this study, however, all materials were tested in the "as fabricated" condition with no special heat treatment other than that associated with extrusion and strain gage bonding at 149°C (300°F) for 2½ hours.

Densities of the unextruded ingots and extruded rods are given in Table I, along with the volume percent of reinforcement. For the composite, the ingot density is slightly lower than the rod density. This could be due to either measurement inaccuracies or to voids being closed during extrusion. The amount of reinforcement was determined by the rule of mixtures assuming a SiC density of 3.197 g/cm^3 (4,5).

Table I. Density and Percent Reinforcement

Material	Ingot Density (g/cm^3)*	Rod Density (g/cm^3)*	Reinforcement (vol. %)
SiC/2024 Al	2.83	2.86	21.0
2024 Al Control	2.76	2.76	--

* $1 \text{ g/cm}^3 = 0.03613 \text{ lb/in}^3$

In two preliminary tests, failures occurred at the specimen shoulders and the fracture data were not valid. To solve this problem, 25.4 mm (1.00 inch) long specimens with a double reduction gage section of the design shown in Figure 1 were used for all remaining tests. Load versus longitudinal strain curves were measured using two strain gages bonded to opposite sides of each specimen with an epoxy-phenolic adhesive. Both the gages and the adhesive were rated for limited service to 370°C (700°F). Despite care in applying the gages, some failures were encountered, and, as a backup a separate load-crosshead deflection curve was recorded during most of the tests. Comparison of the results for 12 specimens where both types of data are available show a mean difference in yield strength for the same sample of 5 percent and that the load-strain curve gives the higher yield strength for 6 of the 12 specimens. Based on this comparison, the two curves were judged to be equivalent.

Specimens were heated with a 3 zone, high intensity, tungsten lamp furnace having a 57 mm (2.25 inch) long heating zone. The center lamp was disconnected to prevent the non-conducting strain gage backing from getting too hot. Dimensions were such that the grips were heated with the top and bottom lamps and the heat flowed into the sample across the specimen/grip

Fig. 1 - Schematic of the tensile specimen showing the double reduction gage section, the location of the strain gages, and the method of attaching the thermocouple leads. Dimensions are in mm (1 mm = 0.0394 inches).

interface. A 10 kg (22 lb) tensile load was maintained during heating to assure good thermal conductivity between the specimen and the grips. Electrical currents to the furnace were determined by two process controllers, each adjusted to provide rapid heat-up with no overshoot and regulated by their own thermocouple attached to the appropriate grip.

Temperatures at the specimen head were measured with 0.15 mm (0.006 inch) diameter thermocouple wires, as shown in Figure 1. Positive and negative wires were inserted and staked into separate 0.35 mm (0.014 inch) diameter holes to form an intrinsic couple, care was taken to assure that the only conducting path between the wires was through the specimen, and a drop of barrier coat was applied to insulate the area from direct heat input. Preliminary heating tests were conducted with thermocouples embedded in holes drilled in the gage section and in the specimen head. This specimen, which was not tensile tested, verified that the time to achieve a steady state condition at the gage section was only a few seconds longer than at the head and that the final temperatures at the two locations were the same.

Elevated temperature tests were conducted by heating the specimens for 90 seconds, with approximately 30 seconds required for heat-up and the remaining 60 seconds used for an elevated temperature soak. Specimens were tensile tested at a crosshead speed of 5.1 mm/min (0.20 inches/min.). For a rigid machine, this would correspond to a strain rate of $5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ sec}^{-1}$.

Results

Figure 2 gives the temperature dependence of the Young's elastic modulus. In determining the modulus, calibration curves provided with the strain gages were used to correct for the temperature dependence of the gage factor. Straight lines with negative slopes have been drawn through the data in agreement with the results reported in the literature for wrought aluminum (6). Room temperature elastic modulus, obtained by applying small loads to the samples prior to the elevated temperature tests, and the plotted

Fig. 2 - Temperature dependence of the Young's elastic modulus for SiC/Al and for a 2024 Al control tested using the same procedures. (1 GPa = 0.145×10^6 psi.)

elevated temperature values show that the SiC reinforced composite is 50 percent stiffer than unreinforced wrought aluminum and that this increase in stiffness is maintained to at least 300°C (570°F).

A similar, but in some ways more significant, comparison can be made based on the specific elastic modulus, which is defined as the Young's elastic modulus divided by the mass per unit volume. Figure 3 gives the temperature dependence of the specific modulus in units of $Mm^2 \cdot s^{-2}$ ($in^2 \cdot sec^{-2}$). Since the SiC/Al composite is only 3 percent more dense than aluminum, it has a 45 to 50 percent greater stiffness than wrought aluminum, whether the comparison is based on Young's modulus or specific modulus.

Temperature dependence of the 0.2 percent offset yield strength is plotted in Figure 4. At temperatures less than 200°C (390°F), the SiC reinforced aluminum had a 0.2 percent offset yield strength of 293 MPa (42.5 ksi). This is 30 percent greater than the value for the aluminum control which had the same thermomechanical history. For temperatures greater than 200°C (390°F), the yield strengths of both materials are temperature dependent. There is some scatter, but, at a given strength level, the SiC/Al composite appears to be capable of withstanding roughly 20°C (36°F) higher temperatures than the unreinforced aluminum.

Figure 5 gives the temperature dependence of the engineering ultimate tensile strength for the SiC/Al composite and the aluminum control. When the temperatures are less than 200°C (390°F), the SiC/Al is 15 percent stronger than the unreinforced aluminum. Between 250 and 300°C (480 and 570°F), the SiC whiskers appear to bring about roughly a 15°C (27°F) increase in temperature range for a given short time strength requirement.

Fig. 3 - Temperature dependence of the specific elastic modulus for SiC/Al and for a 2024 Al control tested using the same procedures. (In a standard gravimetric field, $1 \text{ Mm}^2 \cdot \text{s}^{-2} = 0.102 \text{ Mm} = 4.01 \times 10^6 \text{ inches.}$)

Fig. 4 - The 0.2% offset yield strength versus temperature for the SiC/Al composite and for the 2024 Al control. (1 MPa = 0.145 ksi.)

Fig. 5 - Ultimate tensile strength as a function of temperature for the SiC/Al composite and for the 2024 Al control. (1 MPa = 0.145 ksi.)

Plastic fracture strains, defined as the total fracture strain minus the elastic component, are given in Figure 6 as a function of temperature. At temperatures less than 240°C (460°F), the composite failed with relatively little plastic flow and no necking. Fracture strains for these specimens were calculated from load-time records. Composite specimens tested at higher temperatures and all of the aluminum control samples displayed substantial plastic flow and necked prior to fracture. For the ductile specimens, fracture strains were defined as the true local strains at the neck. These strains were calculated from the initial diameter, D_i , and the minimum diameter at the neck after fracture D_f , by:

$$\epsilon_p = 2 \ln(D_i/D_f) \quad (1)$$

Two methods for measuring strains were used because, at low plastic flow there was no necking and ϵ_p values obtained using Equation 1 were very sensitive to small inaccuracies in measuring D_i and D_f . On the other hand, when strains were large and there was substantial necking, the plastic fracture strains calculated from measured diameters are more meaningful than those calculated from overall specimen elongation.

Discussion

One of the more serious limitations of unreinforced aluminum is its decrease in strength at relatively low elevated temperatures. Reinforcing aluminum with continuous filaments of boron, BORSIC and graphite significantly extends the temperature range of the matrix (7,8,9). Similarly, reinforcing aluminum with Al_2O_3 and SiC whiskers has been shown to improve the high temperature properties of the matrix, but to a lesser degree than the continuous filaments (10,11). Direct comparison between the continuous and discontinuous reinforcement can be deceptive, however, in that axial tensile tests of continuous filament composites are almost always conducted with cool grips

Fig. 6 - Plastic fracture strains plotted on a logarithmic scale versus temperature for the SiC/Al composite and for the 2024 Al control.

and continuous filaments spanning the distance between the grips. As such, the continuous filament high temperature test really measures the fiber bundle strength, which may, or may not, relate to the strength of the composite part, depending on the temperature distribution in the component (12). This is quite different from the hot test of a short fiber composite where the entire filaments are in the hot zone.

The room temperature yield and tensile strengths of certain aluminum alloys, when properly heat treated, are greater than those reported for the SiC/Al composite. This higher strength is generally not useable for structures subjected to prolonged elevated temperature exposure, however, because the material overages and softens with time at temperature. Valid comparisons between the reinforced and unreinforced aluminum, particularly at elevated temperatures, must be based on the same thermomechanical history and the same strain rate. Compared to the aluminum control, the SiC/Al composite showed a significant improvement in strength properties at temperatures less than 240°C (460°F) and a slight improvement in strength properties at higher temperatures, but these improvements were accompanied by an order of magnitude decrease in low temperature fracture strain. There is no known data on the fracture toughness of this composite in the extruded condition but a plastic fracture strain of only 1.4 percent suggests that the toughness of the composite may be somewhat lower than desired.

It had been hoped that the temperature at which the short fiber composite lost its strength would be much higher than wrought aluminum and that this would allow the composite to compete with titanium for certain high temperature applications. For a given strength requirement, SiC whisker reinforcement did result in roughly a 15 to 20°C (27 to 36°F) improvement in the maximum operating temperature compared to unreinforced aluminum. While the change is in the right direction and could effect some borderline cases, the amount of improvement is small and SiC/Al composites are not expected to compete with titanium for high temperature applications.

While the moderate temperature properties of the SiC/Al are encouraging, composites are more expensive than conventional metals and design decisions must be based on the economics of the substitution. The following analysis examines the relationships between the projected cost of the SiC/Al composite and the dollar value which must be placed on a kilogram of weight saved if the substitution is to be justified in stiffness critical structures. Stiffness controlled applications were chosen for evaluation because it was felt that the high elastic modulus is the most outstanding property of the SiC whisker reinforced aluminum.

In this analysis, it was assumed that a structure was initially designed for unreinforced aluminum and that the structural elements were sized based on permitted axial deflections, buckling loads, natural frequencies etc. The approach was to substitute the SiC/Al composite for the aluminum, keeping all loads and dimensions constant except the cross sectional area, which was allowed to vary such that the SiC/Al and the wrought aluminum failed at the same load. The cross sectional dimensions and densities were used to calculate the weight reduction associated with the substitution and the results were expressed as the value of structural weight saved versus the difference in cost between the composite and the unreinforced aluminum. When expressed in this manner, and for the loading conditions considered, the data are independent of the actual dimensions of the components.

Figure 7 shows the relationships between the value of weight saved and the increased material cost for an axially loaded rod that fails when its axial extension under load exceeds a predetermined amount. The whisker manufacturer projects that the SiC/Al composite will cost \$10/kg (\$4.50/lb) more than unreinforced aluminum provided there is sufficient demand to justify volume production using casting and extrusion methods. The present analysis, however, is based on a somewhat less optimistic \$20/kg (\$9.10/lb) differential. At \$20/kg (\$9.10/lb) and a 50% higher modulus for the composite than the aluminum, a design engineer would have to be willing to pay \$43/kg (\$20/lb) for the substitution to be justified, as shown by the dotted lines on the figure. Approximately the same cost relationships apply to a simply supported circular cross section beam when the failure criterion is the minimum natural frequency in bending. Cost relations which are applicable for substitutions based on either general elastic buckling (not localized buckling) or allowable bending deflections of a circular cross section rod are shown in Figure 8. In these cases, the value of weight saved is \$105/kg (\$48/lb) when the modulus increase is 50% and the material cost differential is \$20/kg (\$9.10/lb).

Assuming that the material costs are correct, the break-even value of weight saved should actually be substantially lower than the amount given above because of the progress that is being made in increasing the average whisker length to diameter ratio (by eliminating low aspect ratio particles) and in producing composites with high reinforcement percentages. These advances should lead to composites with moduli of 2 or 2.5 times the moduli of aluminum and this translates to a major reduction in the dollar value of weight saved, as shown in the figures. For example, if the composite modulus can be raised to twice the modulus of aluminum, the break-even value of

Fig. 7 - Value of weight saved vs. (SiC/Al cost-Al cost). Results are for a SiC/Al composite replacing an unreinforced Al structural element that "fails" when its axial deflection under load, ΔL , exceeds a predetermined maximum. Composite moduli are 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 times the modulus of Al.

Fig. 8 - Value of weight saved vs. (SiC/Al cost-Al cost). Results are for a SiC/Al composite replacing an unreinforced Al structural element that "fails" by either elastic buckling or when its bending deflection under load exceeds a predetermined maximum. Composite moduli are 1.5, 2.0, and 2.5 times the modulus of Al.

weight saved which were given above are cut in half.

Conclusions

Aluminum matrix composites reinforced with the inexpensive SiC whiskers produced from rice hulls are new and the only mechanical properties which have been evaluated are strength, stiffness and ductility. Obviously, much developmental work remains to be done. The favorable economic analysis, however, justifies proceeding with these efforts, particularly for stiffness critical components on high performance vehicles.

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